

Ring Transformation of some Indole Derivatives using Phase Transfer Catalysis

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Ring transformation in indole derivatives has been induced by dichlorocarbene in the presence of aqueous KOH with tetrabutylammonium hydrogen sulphate as phase transfer catalyst and 3-haloquinoline (**2**) prepared in good yield. However, the reaction of 3-formyl-2-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)indole (**3**) under similar conditions affords 3-chloro-4-[2,2-dichloro-3-oxiranyl]-2-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)quinoline (**4**). Characterisation of these products has been done by elemental analyses and ir, ^1H nmr, ^{19}F nmr and mass spectral data.

Application of two phase systems is one of the important methodological developments in organic synthesis. The technique can be used for heterocyclic ring transformation. In the present investigation, we wish to report the ring expansion of indole on reaction with dichlorocarbene to 3-haloquinoline under phase transfer condition and the effect of aldehyde functional group in ring transformation. A survey of the literature revealed that although the ring expansion of indole derivatives with poor yields has been done earlier using different catalysts, viz. triethylbenzylammonium chloride and dibenzo-18-crown-6-ether¹⁻³, no reference is available in which tetrabutylammonium hydrogen sulphate (TBAHSO₄) is used. Further, no such reaction on fluorinated analogs has been reported till date. Also, compound having a reactive group on indole, 3-formyl-2-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)indole has been subjected to this type of reaction for the first time. We have made an interesting observation that dichlorocarbene can be used for ring expansion as well as addition to the carbonyl group to afford

3-chloro-4-[2,2-dichloro-3-oxiranyl]-2-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)quinoline (**4**). Although the addition of :CCl₂ to the carbonyl group has been reported earlier⁴, yet no such reaction is known which involves the ring expansion along with addition to carbonyl group.

A solution of appropriate indole in chloroform as the organic phase, and a concentrated KOH solution as the aqueous phase were mixed and stirred at room temperature to yield 3-haloquinoline (**2**, **4**) derivatives which were obtained from the organic phase (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

Structural assignments of the products (Table 1) are based on ir, ^1H nmr, ^{13}C nmr and mass spectral studies. Ir spectrum of **2b** showed the

disappearance of N-H absorption from the region 3 100–3 220 cm^{-1} . In the ^1H nmr only aromatic protons were observed as a multiplet at δ 6.69–7.68. The presence and position of fluorine were confirmed by ^{19}F nmr using hexafluorobenzene as external standard. Fluorine attached to the 4-position of 2-phenylquinoline was observed at δ –110.43 ppm. The mass spectrum of compound showed a molecular ion peak at m/z 257.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF 3-HALOQUINOLINES (2 AND 4)*

Compd no	R ¹	R ²	Yield %	Mp °C
2a	C ₆ H ₅	H	80	190
2b	4-F-C ₆ H ₄	H	75	238d
2c	3-CH ₃ , 4-F-C ₆ H ₃	H	72	140
2d	CH ₃	CH ₃	79	80
4	3-Cl, 4-F-C ₆ H ₃	–	72	192

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

The ir spectrum of compound 4 showed the disappearance of carbonyl as well as N-H absorption bands. In the ^1H nmr a multiplet for aromatic protons at δ 6.80–7.52 and a singlet due to CH proton at δ 4.57 were observed. ^{19}F nmr showed a singlet for fluorine atom attached to the 4-position of 2-phenylquinoline at δ –108.94 ppm. Additional support was obtained by mass spectrum, which showed the molecular ion peak at m/z 403. On the basis of these data, this compound was identified as 4.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr and ^{19}F nmr spectra on a Jeol FX-90Q spectrometer using TMS as internal standard

for ^1H nmr and C₆F₆ as external reference for ^{19}F nmr and mass spectra on MS-30 and MS-50 Kratos spectrometers.

Indole and its derivatives (1a–d and 3) were prepared by Fischer indole method⁵.

3-Haloquinoline (2a–d) and 3-chloro-4-[2,2-dichloro-3-oxiranyl]-2-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)quinoline (4): A mixture of the appropriate indole (0.01 mol) and TBAHSO₄ (0.01 mol) in chloroform (150 ml) was stirred till a clear solution was obtained. An aqueous solution of 50% KOH (20 ml) was added to it dropwise with stirring (0.5 h) and stirring continued for additional 6 h at room temperature. The mixture was then extracted with chloroform, the chloroform-water mixture washed with water and chloroform concentrated. The residue was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel as stationary phase and solvents of increasing polarity were employed as mobile phase.

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